

Original Contribution

Analysis of the Impact of NO₂ Levels on COVID-19 in the San Francisco Bay Area

Benedict Wonjae Song¹✉

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Objective. To explore the influence of ambient air pollutant NO₂ on the COVID-19 ("Co" stands for coronavirus, "Vi" is for virus and "D" is for disease) in the five various counties of the USA.

Methods. Employing openly available data collected by the US Census Bureau, National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), and additional agencies, county-level fatality rates were taken from the literature that was regressed on concentration values of nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) (and ground-level ozone), days since very first approved case. Moreover, On March 19, 2020, a matter regarding the nascent COVID-19 pandemic pushed the Californian government to command lockdown on all Californian residents, except to do certain primary tasks.

Results. The study revealed that NO₂ has a kind of linear correlation with COVID-19 (county-level mortality rates, including some other parameters) that also produced the O₃. Additionally, ground-level ozone is confidently associated with COVID-19 cases (fatality rates). Additionally, as an outcome of lockdown, the usage of individual vehicles drastically lowered. Since these transportations significantly provided to NO₂ levels in five mentioned counties of USA, many have queried whether their absenteeism let a drop in NO₂ pollution.

Conclusions. High NO₂ concentrations and ground-level O₃ object to a higher COVID-19 case and fatality rate. To check additional deaths, it is essential to follow lockdown limitations and also speculate research verdicts in public systems. In the fact of air pollution or contamination, environmental constraints should be augmented, and additional anticipations should be practiced as plants start resuming.

INTRODUCTION

The novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) has negatively influenced a large number of people bodily, psychologically, and economically. First recorded in first December in Wuhan, China, COVID-19 is a respiratory illness with flu-like indications and pneumonitis. Given its incubation phase and tones of transportation, the virus is extremely contagious and expanded instantly globally, challenging numerous lives. As of 27 May 2020, the death toll in the USA had attained 100 000[1]. Globally, investigations have

demonstrated that COVID-19 is extra deadly amongst certain societies, for example, adults aged ≥ 65 years and physiquess with cardiovascular and underlying respiratory health conditions[2]. It is critical to examine the variables that impact COVID-19 deaths, to limit the mortality rate from progressing. This investigation aims to estimate a possible association between COVID-19 mortality and NO₂ air pollutants in five USA counties. The five primary air pollutants are nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) ground level ozone (O₃), sulfur dioxide (SO₂) carbon monoxide (CO), and particulate matter 2.5. All certain pollutants are recognized to be linked with

¹Homestead High School, 21370 Homestead Rd, Cupertino, CA 95014, United States

✉Corresponding email: benedict04song@gmail.com

adverse fatal impacts on wellness, including cardiovascular disease, stroke and lung cancer. For instance, NO₂ is damaging to individual health by destroying lung linings and inciting other severe respiratory ailments. Basically, air contamination dysregulates antiviral resistant responses and increases cardiovascular and respiratory conditions[3]. As those pollution-induced health situations are the very identical conditions that boost the probability of COVID-19 loss, it is understandable to hypothesize that raised ambient air pollutant concentration is correlated with costlier COVID-19 fatality rates. Current investigations assessing the correlation of NO₂ and fatality rates in regions of England[4] and northern Italy[5] also conferred a linear correlation.

Gaseous nitrogen oxides account for a significant portion of smog over major cities. These reactive gases cause respiratory distress in low concentrations and contribute to bronchitis and pneumonia at higher concentrations. Man-made combustion engines, such as those found in cars, trucks, buses, power plants, and off-road equipment, continue to be a major source of NO₂ pollution; as a result, NO₂ concentration tends to be positively correlated with human activity. Nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), and the closely related compound nitrogen monoxide (NO), are natural byproducts of the combustion of fossil fuels. Introduced into the environment through car exhaust and power plant pollution, they account for much of the air pollution in urban and industrial areas, and raise ground-level ozone concentrations through spontaneous reactions triggered by light energy. These pollutants, along with the ozone they produce, are known to be extremely harmful to the lungs and airways. They also contribute significantly to rain acidification, which erodes buildings and damages soil.

Recent, the still-ongoing worldwide COVID-19 pandemic forced much of the world to impose lockdown and shelter-in-place measures, which caused the halting of much industrial activity. Because a significant portion of nitrogen oxide pollution originates from these industrial activities, a natural question to consider is whether the COVID-19 lockdowns significantly impacted NO₂ levels. This study aims to assess the effect of NO₂ on COVID-19 and the March 19 Bay Area COVID-19 lockdown on NO₂ levels within the San Francisco Bay Area-- in particular, within the five California counties (San Francisco, San Mateo, Santa Clara, Alameda, and Contra Costa) that comprise the Bay Area.

NO₂ production in public atmospheres is due to photochemical activity. NO₂ is not usually deemed a primary pollutant as is NO, however is somewhat a secondary pollutant, photochemically "produced" in the

atmosphere, and with inherent health indications. It is subject to the brownish-hued skies on days of high pollution. NO₂ has for years been ascertained continuously in ambient air with the aid of Saltzman³ reagent. From two decades of perpetual NO₂ determination, it has not been contracted an analogous long term manual method. Certainly, till newly, it has not been a necessity for such an analytic method.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Data

We collected NO₂, (county-level) air pollutant design values and time-averaged map (total column) from the NASA website [10]. The NO₂, the design annually and monthly (2018, 2019, 2020, and 2021-till now) values were measured in parts per billion (ppb). For fatality measures, we took the figure of COVID-19 losses from already reported data that were gathered from the USAF acts website,² which collected data from the U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) and local agencies, reference state signified each county's total COVID-19 deaths at various times.

Methods

In order to assess the effect of the March 19 lockdowns on NO₂ levels in the Bay Area, daily NO₂ levels (in ppb) from 5 different Bay Area counties (San Francisco, San Mateo, Santa Clara, Alameda, Contra Costa) between 2019-01-01 and 2021-07-30 were analyzed and plotted. Each county was represented by a randomly chosen site in the EPA [10] and NASA (Appendix 1 and 2-8) [11] database.

Through the use of a custom python script[6], the data was summed to calculate daily total NO₂ concentration, and compiled into a single spreadsheet. The spreadsheet was then plotted, with date as the independent variable and total NO₂ concentration as the dependent variable. Mean NO₂ levels from Jan 2019 (date of California shelter-in-place) up until 2021-7-31, were calculated. Mean levels from these date intervals, but in 2019 and 2020, were also calculated to account for seasonal variance. A chi-squared test (N = 3) was then performed on these four means in order to assess the impact of the March 19 COVID-19 lockdowns on NO₂ levels Appendix figure 1.

NO₂ level data was taken from the EPA. Daily data from five Bay Area counties (San Francisco, San Mateo, Santa Clara, Alameda, and Contra Costa) was examined. From each county, a random testing site and its recorded data were selected to represent that county.

The data for each day was then summed, compiled into a spreadsheet, and plotted. Appendix 1 shows a clear annually cyclic nature to the NO₂ concentration with respect to time; the concentrations peak near the holiday season (Nov-Dec) and taper off during the summer (May-Aug). From examining the peaks and dips of the 2020 cycle, and comparing these to the historical record (2019, 2020), it can be observed that the 2019 peak is much greater in magnitude than that of 2020 or 2021, while the 2021 dip is slightly lower than that of 2019 and 2020.

Table 1: A table of NO₂ levels comparing mean NO₂ levels from before 3/19 and following 3/19, including both the historical average (2018-2019) and the target year (2020). A chi-squared test (N = 3) was performed on the above table in order to assess the impact of the March 19 COVID-19 lockdowns, while accounting for seasonal variances in NO₂ levels.

Year	Mean of NO ₂ levels 74 days before 3/19	Mean of NO ₂ levels 74 days following 3/19
Historical Average (2018-2019)	118 ppb	72 ppb
2020	114 ppb	52 ppb

RESULTS

On correlated variables omitted, concentrations of both NO₂ and O₃ exhibit vital ties with COVID-19 positive cases and fatality rate. As know Nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), and the closely related compound nitrogen monoxide (NO), are natural byproducts of the combustion of fossil fuels. Introduced into the environment through car exhaust and power plant pollution, they account for much of the air pollution in urban and industrial areas, and raise ground-level ozone concentrations through spontaneous reactions triggered by light energy. Concretely, while concentrations of O₃ boost by 1 ppm, the fatality rate jumps by 0.857%. While concentrations of NO₂ rise by 1 ppb, the fatality rate jumps by 0.002%. This conclusion for NO₂ is logical with inquiries carried in various parts of the world that observed a real correlation between NO₂ and enhanced risk of COVID-19 loss. Moreover, statistically meaningful NO₂ drops were observed through the current COVID-19 season correlated to historical data: a 25.5% decline with an absolute reduction of 4.8 ppb in metropolitan counties and counties from kingdoms initiating early non-essential market cessations. Knowing how air pollution is influenced throughout COVID-19 pandemic will

afford significant evidence concerning health consequences and check of emissions [7]. On March 19, 2020, concerns about the nascent COVID-19 pandemic spurred California governor Gavin Newsom to impose shelter-in-place restrictions on all Californian citizens. Among other things, the restrictions barred Californians from leaving their homes, except to perform certain essential tasks. As a result, the usage of personal vehicles drastically decreased. Since these vehicles significantly contributed to NO_x levels in California, many have wondered whether their absence caused a decrease in NO₂ pollution.

San Francisco

In FEB. 25, state of emergency was declared and on March 11, cancellation gathering of more than 250 people was announced but on March 15, all bars, nightclubs, wineries, and brewpubs to close, but allows restaurants to stay open but to reduce capacity so customers are socially distanced. As cases were increased in all five counties so on march 17 shelter in place ordered that extend through May 3. On May 28 gradual reopening of schools, sports, gyms and restaurants were announced, but on June 29, citing a sharp increase in cases overnight so restrictions were increased. Anyhow, on July 1, indoor reopening was allowed but on July 13 Paused reopening plan as cases exceed from 4000 but school and zoo reopening plan. Due to this reopening (of transportation) on August 5, more than 7,000 diagnosed cases. On Sep 14 first time Reopening the business and indoor activities at that time highest number of patients in hospital were recorded. So, on Nov. 28 tougher restrictions were pointed and on December 2 10 days quarantine for in out travel but gradually cases were decreased and on March 3 allows indoor dining, indoor gyms and on July positivity rate average tops 3 percent.

San Mateo

From March 15-17, all bars, nightclubs, wineries, and brewpubs to close, but allows restaurants to stay open but to reduce capacity so customers kept at socially distanced. Anyhow less cases were observed in San Mateo still on July 16 San Mateo County is not on the watch list and due to increase in cases in vicinity of San Mateo on November 28 tougher restrictions were pointed but there was not that harm was observed in San Mateo as the NO₂ conc. was not too alarming here.

Santa Clara

Santa Clara was the first county I which first confirmed COVID-19 case was reported on Jan. 24, also first death was recorded on FEB. 6 and on March 13, second death

reported. So, it was alarming for USA and they decided on March 15, all bars, nightclubs, wineries, and brewpubs to close, but allows restaurants to stay open but to reduce capacity so customers should be socially distanced and on MARCH 17 shelter in place order. Anyhow govt. decided to reopen outdoor activities on July 12 but the decision was not that good and on July 16, Santa Clara reported more than 7,000 diagnosed cases and become First County that has 21,840 cases and surpasses Alameda County with 21,708 cases. On Nov. 25, 512 new cases so govt. started vaccination on Dec. 17 and on Jan. 14, pandemic death toll tops 1,000. Jan. was not good enough for the Sant Clara as on Jan 28 exceed 100,000 diagnosed cases and more than 1,500 deaths as the NO₂ was too heigh in that area. Anyhow, after vaccination on March 3 allows indoor dining, indoor gyms and decline in cases were observed till today.

Alameda

On March 15, all bars, nightclubs, wineries, and brewpubs to close, but allows restaurants to stay open but to reduce capacity so customers are socially distanced on doing that still cases were increased so on MARCH 17 shelter in place order that o body can move to rash area. Anyhow despite doing that on July 2, exceeds 6,000 diagnosed cases so they paused reopening plan on July 13 as cases exceeding 7,000. So, July 10 2020 shut down outdoor dining, on July 14 additional restrictions were pointed as Alameda County becomes the first in the Bay Area to exceed 8,000 diagnosed cases anyhow on August 28 allowed for more outdoor business activity that cause more than 20,000 diagnosed cases on Sep. 14. Any how they have started vaccination on December 17 but at that time already confirmed cases lead to causalities till Feb 4 1,000 coronavirus deaths were recorded. Anyhow for now in July positivity rate is 3 percent, the decline in percentage may be due to reduction of NO₂.

Contra Costa

Similar to all other counties in Contra Costa from March 15-17, all bars, nightclubs, wineries, and brewpubs to close, but allows restaurants to stay open but to reduce capacity so customers are socially distanced that included in shelter in place order. Anyhow on June 17, the 50th death from coronavirus were reported still some services kept reopen till July 1 2020, along with dine-in restaurants, bars, gyms, museums, hotels, indoor religious services. In conclusion on July 14 more than 5,000 cases of coronavirus anyhow till today after Sam Mateo Contra Costa is less affected by COVID-19 as the NO₂ was kept low by the human activities.

DISCUSSION

It is necessary to remark that ground-level O₃ and stratospheric O₃ are very diverse in their outcomes. While stratospheric O₃ produces the O₃ layer that checks out destructive ultraviolet radiation and is constituted from spontaneous chemical-processes, ground-level O₃ is a part of smog and is risen from nitrogen oxides (NO_x) usually vented into the atmosphere during manmade practices before-mentioned industrial discharges and vehicle exhaust. So, NO₂ is a sort of nitrogen oxide (NO_x), it illustrates the binary consequence of the influence of NO₂ and O₃ on the COVID-19 fatality rate. Various researches conveyed on ground-level O₃ have explained its linear correlation with negative cardiovascular and respiratory health upshots. In China, where great levels of smog have generated dangerous living contingencies, a predicted 230 000 to 403 000 respiratory-related mortality were due to long-term ozone appearance in 2016. The preexisting inopportune health impacts produced by expression to O₃ execute selves more receptive to COVID-19-related loss, due to vulnerable cardiovascular, respiratory, and immune functions. This correlation was identified through the 2002 SARS revolution, in which research explicated that SARS victims from Chinese areas with an average air pollution index had an 84% raised prospect of vanishing than those from regions with low APIs (in which O₃ is included). With the currently mandated lockdowns, there has been a global improvement in air quality because of the interim cessation of factories and the shrinkage of in-vehicle use. Notwithstanding, the decline in NO₂ concentration, research assessing European towns and Wuhan noticed an uptick in the ozone of 17% in Europe and 36% because of the reduced NO₂ titration of ozone, respectively. As to lands such as the US resume, contamination levels will gradually start to revert to pre-COVID-19 levels. Despite a semi-centennial spell approaching a clearer atmosphere and greener dilemmas, air pollutants yet perform a massive part in creating unfavorable health consequences, and more stringent norms must be practiced to check emissions. O₃ has been disregarded when it comes to controlling. In the United States in 2016, 90% of disagreement to the national ambient air quality norms was about O₃, whereas only 10% was in association to NO₂ and other pollutants. The COVID-19 pandemic only further certainly highlights the vital and harmful consequences of air pollution, which has been a rising dilemma for years. Very latterly, to resist the economic mess, the US air pollutant constraints are being released to admit restoration and incentivize composition. It is remarkably challenging to balance economic continuity with COVID-19 losses but exerting defensive actions by further checking contamination may be extra socially

and economically efficient in the long term. Modern research by Wang et al. concluded that if severe measures are practiced to lessen the emissions of greenhouse gas and air pollution in the US especially California counties, there will be a proposed 14 000 untimely losses stopped in the state in 2050, as well as lessened cardiovascular and respiratory-related hospital appointments[8, 9]. By approving propositions such as incentives for electric vehicle ownership and realizing more green energy choices ground level O₃ can be overcome besides other pollutants.

Jan-March 2020

In **San Francisco** on FEB. 25, state of emergency was declared and on MARCH 11, CANCELLATION gathering of more than 250 people was announced but on March 15, all bars, nightclubs, wineries, and brewpubs to close, but allows restaurants to stay open but to reduce capacity so customers are socially distanced. As cases were increased in all five counties so on MARCH 17 shelter in place ordered that extend through May 3. In **San Mateo** during this period all bars, nightclubs, wineries, and brewpubs to close, but allows restaurants to stay open but to reduce capacity so customers kept at socially distanced. During this stage **Santa Clara** was the first county I which first confirmed COVID-19 case was reported on Jan. 24, also first death was recorded on FEB. 6 and on March 13, second death reported. So, it was alarming for USA and they decided on March 15, all bars, nightclubs, wineries, and brewpubs to close, but allows restaurants to stay open but to reduce capacity so customers should be socially distanced and on MARCH 17 shelter in place order. **Alameda** on during that period was much affected, all bars, nightclubs, wineries, and brewpubs to close, but allows restaurants to stay open but to reduce capacity so customers are socially distanced on doing that still cases were increased so on MARCH 17 shelter in place order that o body can move to rash area. Anyhow despite doing that on July 2, exceeds 6,000 diagnosed cases so they paused reopening plan on July 13 as cases exceeding 7,000. **Contra Costa** during that period was not that affected similar to San Mateo, all bars, nightclubs, wineries, and brewpubs to close, but allows restaurants to stay open but to reduce capacity so customers are socially distanced that included in shelter in place order (Appendix 9).

April-June 2020

San Francisco On May 28 gradual reopening of schools, sports, gyms and restaurants were announced, but on June 29, citing a sharp increase in cases overnight so restrictions were increased. In **Contra Costa** anyhow

on June 17, the 50th death from coronavirus were reported but remaining counties were stable this period.

July-September 2020

In **San Francisco** anyhow, on July 1, indoor reopening was allowed but on July 13 Paused reopening plan as cases exceed from 4000 but school and zoo reopening plan. In **Santa Clara** anyhow govt. decided to reopen outdoor activities on July 12 but the decision was not that good and on July 16, Santa Clara reported more than 7,000 diagnosed cases and become First County that has 21,840 cases and surpasses Alameda County with 21,708 cases. **San Mateo** during this period (on July 16) San Mateo County is not on the watch. During this stage **Alameda** on during that period was much affected, July 2, exceeds 6,000 diagnosed cases so they paused reopening plan on July 13 as cases exceeding 7,000. **Contra Costa** that period was not that affected similar to San Mateo, till July 1 2020, along with dine-in restaurants, bars, gyms, museums, hotels, indoor religious services. In conclusion on July 14 more than 5,000 cases were reported.

Oct.-Dec. 2020

In **San Francisco** so, on Nov. 28 tougher restrictions were pointed and on December 2 10 days quarantine for in out travel but gradually cases were decreased. In **Santa Clara** on Nov. 25, 512 new cases and pandemic death toll tops 1,000. **Alameda** cause more than 20,000 diagnosed cases on Sep. 14 were recorded. **Contra Costa** and **San Mateo** during this period was not on the watch list.

Jan-March. 2021

In **San Francisco** March 3 allows indoor dining, indoor gyms and on July positivity rate average tops 3 percent. In **Santa** Jan 28 exceed 100,000 diagnosed cases and more than 1,500 deaths as the NO₂ was too heigh in that area. **Alameda** till Feb 4 1,000 coronavirus deaths were recorded. **Contra Costa** and **San Mateo** during this period was not on the watch list.

On the other hand, form Dec. 2019 to Jan. 2020 and from Dec. 2020 to Jan. 2021 the concentration of NO₂ was too high (especially in Alameda and Santa Clara counties) from the rest of the month of the years. So, during winter season the concentration of NO₂ remains high (see Appendix figure 1 and 2) but during that period COVID cases were not to heigh (Jan-March 2020) see Appendix 8. In San Francisco more than 4,000 COVID cases were reported in July and in the same month Santa Clara reported more than 7,000 diagnosed cases and exceeded in number (21, 840) from Alameda

that has 21,708 cases. Almost July was harmful for all counties except San Mateo and Contra Costa but if we see from Appendix 2 and 6 during that period NO₂ conc. was not that alarming. From July-Dec. 2020 tougher restriction were pointed in San Francisco but this period was to alarming for Santra Clara as 1,000 deaths were reported till that date. Alameda facing trouble because has reached to 20,000 confirmed cases. During that period the conc. of NO₂ was too heigh especially in Santra Clara and Alameda (Appendix 1 and 2-8).

So, it is concluded that two counties Santra Clara and Alameda were directly affected July-Dec. but we can also say that NO₂ has effect on COVID-19 as its conc. reach at harsh point. Like during winter season its conc. remains high but covid cases were in control but during summer season cases started enhancing. So, it means NO₂ not affected that directly but after one to three months. On the other side, Lockdown has also direct effect on NO₂ conc. As we can see lockdown was started in March 2020 it reduced the usage of vehicles that cases the lessen of air pollution and its results appeared in whole summer season (that is decrease in conc.). But as Govt. allows the transportation it cases the enhancement in pollution (during Dec-Jan 2021). So, we can also say on the production of NO₂ ozone is also produced that case more effect on COVID-19. Anyhow, in Appendix 2 and 8 we can see the conc. of NO₂ is too low till today in particular areas, we can say it is due lockdown but after resuming it can be enhanced so we can take some precautionary measures.

CONCLUSION

This research renders observational proof that NO₂ is also significantly correlated with the COVID-19 mortality rate (as is causes the production of ground-level O₃ that is associated with COVID-19 fatality rate. This knowledge was subjected to various constraints that could result in mistakes. There are yet other factors that were not considered for, that are responsible for COVID 19. The representation the area was also small (five counties), as the number of county-level observations extorted from the NASA data was a

fraction of the USs' total 3,141 counties. Inside this short number of counties, some outliers appeared from the demographic and geographic diversity, varying from remarkably densely populated counties to separate and sparsely populated counties. Given certain and other barriers, additional investigation and examination on the relationship of air pollution and COVID-19 should be managed to convey about a careful opinion of aforementioned novel virus, as a viable other wave is on the skyline.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Plot of NO₂ levels (ppb) against date (ranging from 2019-01-01 and 2021-07-30)

Appendix 2: Red spot showing the NO₂ contamination over five mentioned counties from March 2018-2019

Appendix 3: Red spot showing the NO₂ contamination over five mentioned counties from March 2019-2020.

Appendix 4: Red spot showing the NO₂ contamination over five mentioned counties from Jun-July 2019.

Appendix 5: Red spot showing the NO₂ contamination over five mentioned counties from Nov.-Dec. 2019.

Appendix 6: Red spot showing the NO₂ contamination over five mentioned counties from Jun.-July 2020.

Appendix 7: Red spot showing the NO₂ contamination over five mentioned counties from Nov.-Dec. 2020.

Appendix 8: Red spot showing the NO₂ contamination over five mentioned counties from Dec. 2020-July 2021.

Appendix 9: all the data from March 17 to July 2021 in all five counties.

Counties	Jan-March 2020	April-June 2020	July-Sep. 2020	Oct.-Dec. 2020	Jan.-March 2021	April-July 2021
San Francisco	<p>1. FEB. 25, state of emergency</p> <p>2. MARCH 11, CANCELLATION gathering of more than 250 people</p> <p>3. March 15, all bars, nightclubs, wineries, and brewpubs to close, but allows restaurants to stay open but to reduce capacity so customers are socially distanced</p> <p>4. MARCH 17 shelter in place order</p>	<p>1. MARCH 17 shelter in place order and extend through May 3</p> <p>2. MAY 18, allows most stores to offer curbside service to shoppers</p> <p>3. May 28 gradual reopening of schools, sports, gyms and restaurants</p> <p>4. June 18, more than 3,000 diagnosed cases.</p> <p>5. June 29, citing a sharp increase in cases overnight</p>	<p>1. July 1, indoor reopen</p> <p>2. July 13 Paused reopening plan as cases exceed from 4000 but school and zoo reopening plan</p> <p>3. July 16 closure indoor.</p> <p>4. August 5, more than 7,000 diagnosed cases.</p> <p>Sep 14 first time Reopening the business and indoor activities with highest number of patients in hospital</p>	<p>1. Nov. 28 tougher restrictions</p> <p>December 2. 17 10 days quarantine in out travel</p>	<p>1. March 3 allows indoor dining, indoor gyms</p>	<p>1. Jul. positivity rate average tops 3 percent</p>
San Mateo	<p>1. March 15, all bars, nightclubs, wineries, and brewpubs to close, but allows restaurants to stay open but to reduce capacity so customers are socially distanced</p> <p>MARCH 17 shelter in place order</p>		<p>1. July 16 San Mateo County is not on the watch list</p>	<p>1. November 28 tougher restrictions</p>		<p>1. Jul. positivity rate average tops 3 percent</p>
Santa Clara	<p>1. First case Jan. 24</p> <p>first death FEB. 6</p> <p>March 13, second death reported</p> <p>March 15, all bars, nightclubs, wineries, and brewpubs to close, but allows restaurants to stay open but to reduce capacity so customers are socially distanced</p> <p>MARCH 17 shelter in place order</p>		<p>1. outdoor activities expect to reopen on July 12.</p> <p>2. July 13, exceeds 6,000 diagnosed cases</p> <p>3. July 16, more than 7,000 diagnosed cases</p>	<p>1. County has 21,840 cases and surpasses Alameda County that has 21,708.</p> <p>2. Nov. 25, 512 new cases.</p> <p>3. Dec. 17 vaccination start</p>	<p>1. Jan. 14, pandemic death toll tops 1,000</p> <p>2. Jan 28 exceed 100,000 diagnosed cases</p> <p>3. Feb 4 more than 1,500 deaths</p> <p>4. March 3 allows indoor dining, indoor gyms</p>	<p>1. Jul. positivity rate average tops 3 percent</p>
Alameda	<p>1. March 15, all bars, nightclubs, wineries, and brewpubs to close, but allows restaurants to stay open but to reduce capacity so customers are socially distanced</p> <p>2. MARCH 17 shelter in place order</p>		<p>1. July 2, exceeds 6,000 diagnosed cases</p> <p>2. July 13 Paused reopening plan as cases exceeding 7,000</p> <p>3. July 10, 2020 shut down outdoor dining</p> <p>4. July 12 additional restrictions</p> <p>5. July 14, 2020 Alameda County becomes the</p>	<p>1. December 17 vaccination start</p>	<p>1. Jan 14 deaths with 776</p> <p>2. Feb 4 1,000 coronavirus deaths</p>	<p>1. Jul. positivity rate average tops 3 percent</p>

			<p>first in the Bay Area to exceed 8,000 diagnosed cases</p> <p>6. August 28 allows for more outdoor business activity</p> <p>7. Sep. 14 has more than 20,000 diagnosed cases</p>			
Contra Costa	<p>1. March 15, all bars, nightclubs, wineries, and brewpubs to close, but allows restaurants to stay open but to reduce capacity so customers are socially distanced</p> <p>2. MARCH 17 shelter in place order</p>	<p>1. June 17, the 50th death from coronavirus reported</p>	<p>1. Some services reopen on July 1, along with dine-in restaurants, bars, gyms, museums, hotels, indoor religious services.</p> <p>2. July 14 more than 5,000 cases of coronavirus</p> <p>3. August 28 allows to begin, along with some other operations.</p>			<p>1. Jul. positivity rate average tops 3 percent</p>

Data was taken from <https://abc7news.com/timeline-of-coronavirus-us-covid-19-bay-area-sf/6047519/> and <https://projects.sfchronicle.com/2020/coronavirus-timeline/>